

Tailored Hydrophobic/Hydrophilic Lignin Coatings on SiO₂ for Sustainable Cobalt(II) Recycling

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ABSTRACT: Lignin is a renewable biopolymer and its chemical functionalization renders it a prospective material for a plethora of applications. Within this respect, we present a rapid method for lignin immobilization on the surface of mesoporous silica. Two types of lignin were used to prove the feasibility of the fabrication of either hydrophilic and hydrophobic biocoatings on silica. The developed procedure enables to immobilize 17 mg of lignosulfonate (LS) or 37 mg of kraft lignin (KL) per gram of silica. The bio-inorganic composites display a synergistic effect in the adsorption of cobalt(II) ions from aqueous solutions, because the adsorption efficiency outperforms clearly the individual constituents. These results demonstrate that thin lignin overlayers, exhibiting polymer concentrations of 0.07 mg·m⁻² for LS-SiO₂ and 0.14 mg·m⁻² for KL-SiO₂, provide new functionality in comparison to bulk lignin and metal oxides. According to the Langmuir isotherm model, the adsorption capacity towards aqua complexes of Co(II) was found to be 75 mg·g⁻¹ and 59 mg·g⁻¹ for the LS- or KL-coated silica, respectively. The kinetics study revealed that lignin-SiO₂ composites gained the features of inorganic sorbents, as 1 – 1.5 hour was sufficient for effective cobalt extraction by lignin-coated silica while the adsorption occurred via the pseudo-second-order kinetics model. The adsorption of Co(II) ions on the bio-inorganic composites was confirmed by solid-state ¹H MAS NMR spectra. The simplicity of the synthesis, low-cost and availability of initial materials, high capacity and adsorption rate, and recyclability makes lignin-coated silica a promising material for cobalt recovery.

INTRODUCTION

In the wake of the technological advance, Li-ion batteries have become a cornerstone to modern society. They are used in small electronic devices such as mobile phones and laptops, as well as in electrical cars. Cobalt has been until today the most important critical raw material (CRM) for cathodes in Li-ion batteries.¹ However, cobalt can be found in sufficient amounts only in few regions in the world, mainly in the Democratic Republic of Congo, where the safe production standards are not always met. Ensuring the supply of CRMs by decoupling it from such production processes is of high importance for a sustainable society and to prevent short-term price fluctuations.² Since cobalt is not only used in batteries, but also as a catalyst and for various steels and alloys, there is a great demand for this metal.³ Therefore, recovering of cobalt from the cathode of used lithium-ion batteries poses one viable option. Although there are already recycling methods based on chemical separation for cathode materials from used Li-ion batteries, novel methods for cobalt recovery have received lots of interest.

The classic pyrometallurgical recovery process consists of melting cells at very high temperatures (over 1400 °C).⁴ This is inevitable connected to the high energy usage and high costs, which represent drawback of the method. Furthermore, the electrolyte and organic binders form volatile gases at low temperatures.² Another promising methods is hydrometallurgy, which can also be conducted as a second step after the pyrometallurgical recovery.⁵ While most inorganic acids give high efficiencies when being used in combination with hydrogen peroxide, their application results in substantial secondary pollution.⁴ Further purification and separation of the metals is done via solvent extraction with various organic compounds. Recently, deep eutectic solvents (DES) have been proposed as ‘green solvents for metal extraction. A DES composed of choline chloride

and ethylene glycol has been used successfully to extract cobalt from lithium cobalt oxide with high efficiency. The subsequent recovery of cobalt via precipitation is difficult since the initial precipitate consists of different species, e.g. cobalt carbonate and oxide. Cobalt can also be regained via electrodeposition, which allows the recycling of the DES, but this method is accompanied with high energy costs.⁶ Furthermore, ethylene glycol is toxic to both humans and animals and can lead to seizures and cardiac arrest within hours if a large enough volume is ingested.⁷ Cobalt can also be recycled using biometallurgy, where inorganic or organic acids are produced by bacteria and then used to leach the metal from the cathode. While this method is very cost-effective, the efficiency is much lower than for hydrometallurgy and the process takes much longer.⁴

A method to regain cobalt from aqueous media would, not only be beneficial to the economy as an additional source for cobalt as a CRM, but also provide a cleaner environment by removing the harmful metal from wastewaters. While it is possible to remove the metal ions via chemical precipitation, membrane filtration or electrochemical treatment, these methods pose different problems on their own: secondary pollution, high costs or missing infrastructure. An efficient and flexible method for metal recovery is adsorption on functionalized membranes. After adsorption of the cobalt ions onto the sorbent, a desorption step allows to release the metal again; thus separating it from other chemicals found in the original solution.⁸

In order to create both an efficient and sustainable process, the type of sorbent material is decisive. A widely used adsorbent is activated carbon which shows excellent adsorption behaviour due to a high internal surface area and an extensive pore system.⁹ However, this adsorbent is very expensive in regard to capital and recycling costs.¹⁰ Another sorbent material with similar characteristics regarding surface area and porosity

is silica gel. The latter exhibits high thermal stability and can be chemically modified to gain customized composites.¹¹ Biosorbents have gained high attention in recent years due to low costs and high efficiency for adsorption heavy metal ions from aqueous solutions. There are broad sources for biosorbents which may be used, including living organisms (microbial biomass) and waste products of agricultural and other industries.⁸ Living biomass shows disadvantages with respect to required conditions, because bacteria need specific nutrition and maintenance to thrive.¹² Biomass, mostly waste products from various industries and natural polymers, is more versatile and can be used in conditions in which live biomass would be destroyed. Moreover, it can be specifically modified and tailored to further amelioration of its adsorption characteristics. The application of waste materials as biosorbents reduces also the costs of their disposal for the involved industries and the overall amount of waste.^{10,13–15}

A promising material for biosorbents is lignin, which is the second most abundant biopolymer after cellulose. Technical lignin comes from paper and pulp industries, where it is separated from cellulose and more than 500 thousand tonnes are generated annually.¹⁶ There, lignin is necessary for the operation process including chemical recovery and generation of energy. However, some surplus of lignin can be used for value-added applications. Lignin from various biorefinery processes can be considered as the waste and must be utilized at the end of the value chain in the given production process. Lignin is a highly complex and irregular macromolecule with three main building blocks derived from *p*-coumaryl alcohol, coniferyl alcohol, and sinapyl alcohol.¹⁷ Lignin contains a large number of phenolic and carboxylic groups, giving thus the advantage that these functional groups can be deprotonated to subsequently adsorb heavy metal ions.¹⁶ While there are many studies on the adsorption of different heavy metal ions, such as Cu(II) or Pb(II), on different kinds of lignin, just few have tried to adsorb Co(II).¹⁰ Up to now, only modified lignins have been used for the adsorption of cobalt(II) and the adsorption capacities reported were rather low (7.7 mg·g⁻¹).¹⁸ Nevertheless, the fabrication of lignin biocoatings on mesoporous inorganic materials could yield promising materials for sustainable cobalt(II) recycling.^{19–23}

The main aim of this study was development of the protocol for hydrophobic and hydrophilic lignin coatings on mesoporous silica in order to obtain sustainable materials for Co(II) recycling. Different lignin layer concentrations were elucidated to obtain a material with superior lignin/silica ratio for efficient cobalt(II) removal. The effects of the tailored functionality and physico-chemical structure of lignin on the performance of the bio-inorganic composite in cobalt(II) removal were investigated. A detailed adsorption/desorption study was conducted to investigate the influence of different parameters, such as pH, time, temperature, metal ions concentration, and different eluents for the desorption.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials. The Kraft lignin (KL) used was produced using an ultrafiltration unit with a ceramic membrane with a molecular weight cut-off of 5 kDa and was provided by the company Clean Flow Black (Forshaga, Sweden). The lignosulfonic acid sodium salt (LS) with an average Mw of 52 kDa was supplied by Aldrich (St. Louis, USA). The silica gel (0.075–0.250 mm, 150 Å), 4-(2'-Pyridylazo)resorcinol (PAR, 97 %), and sodium tetraborate (Na₂B₄O₇, 98 %, anhydrous) were purchased from Acros organics (Geel, Belgium). Sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 98 %), sodium chloride (NaCl, 99.0 % min.), cobalt(II) nitrate

hexahydrate (Co(NO₃)₂ · 6 H₂O, 97.7 % min.) and (±)-epichlorohydrin (99 %) were obtained from Alfa Aesar (Haverhill, USA). Ethanol (≥99.8 %), nitric acid (HNO₃, 65 %), sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄, 95 %), hydrochloric acid (HCl, 37 %), ammonia solution (NH₃ · H₂O, 25 %) and sodium hydrogen carbonate (NaHCO₃, 100 %) were purchased from VWR (Radnor, USA). All chemicals were used as received without further purification. All solutions were prepared with deionized water.

Synthesis of lignosulfonate-silica (LS-SiO₂) composites. Silica (1 g) was suspended in ethanol (5 mL) and LS (0.5–5 g) in water (5 mL) was added. The mixture was preheated to T~60 °C and continuously mixed on mechanical stirrer. A solution of epichlorohydrin (0.1 mL) in ethanol (5 mL) was added dropwise slowly to the mixture. After addition of NaHCO₃ (0.05 g) the reaction mixture was heated to boiling (T~85 °C) for 25 min under vigorous stirring. The obtained solids were filtered off and washed repeatedly with cold and hot di-ionized water as well as ethanol. After drying at 50 °C for 1 day, a light brown solid material (0.85 g, weight yield~57%) was obtained.

Synthesis of kraft lignin-silica gel (KL-SiO₂) composite. The procedure is the same as described for LS-SiO₂ composite. The KL was dissolved in a solvent mixture of ethanol and water (4 : 1.10 mL). Weight yield was 0.9 g (60%).

Characterization. IR spectra were collected using a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (Spotlight 400 FTIR imaging system, Waltham, MA, USA) equipped with a Spectac MKII Golden Gate system (Creekstone Ridge, GA, USA). The samples were analyzed in the range of 600–4000 cm⁻¹ with 16 scans at a four cm⁻¹ resolution and 1 cm⁻¹ interval at room temperature. Thermal analysis was carried out on a TGA/DSC 1 (Mettler Toledo) instrument and Perkin Elmer TGA 7 Thermogravimetric Analyzer. The next operational conditions were applied: a heating rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹, a dynamic atmosphere of synthetic air or nitrogen of 50 mL·min⁻¹, a temperature range of 30–900 °C, and a sample mass of ~2.5 mg.

Low temperature nitrogen-adsorption/desorption experiments were performed to determine the specific surface areas and pore volumes of the composites and initial silica. Specific surface areas were determined from the nitrogen adsorption and desorption data. For this process, an automatic sorption analyzer ASAP 2020 (Micromeritics, USA) was used. The samples were degassed at 120 °C during 10 h before measurements. The analysis report was generated automatically using Micromeritics software. The surface area (*S*_{BET}) was determined by using the following equation based on the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) multilayer adsorption model:

$$S_{BET} = \frac{A_G \cdot Q_{ads} \cdot N_A}{V_m} \quad (1)$$

*A*_G is the occupied area of one gas molecule (m²), *Q*_{Ads} is the quantity of gas molecules adsorbed on the sample (m³·g), *N*_A is the Avogadro constant (mol⁻¹) and *V*_m is the molar volume (m³·mol⁻¹) of the adsorbed gas. The total pore volume (*V*_{Pore}) was determined by single point adsorption at *p/p*⁰ = 0.997 and the average pore diameter was estimated using the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method by using the equation 4 *V*_{Pore}/*S*_{BET} and assuming a cylindrical pore geometry.

The pH of the point of zero charge (pH_{pzc}) was determined for both sorbents using the pH drift method. For this method, the pH of the 0.01 M NaCl solution was adjusted in steps of two between 2 and 12 by adding different volumes of 0.01 M HCl and 0.01 M NaOH. 0.02 g of sorbent was added to 5 mL of the solution and shaken for 24 h. Afterwards, the adsorbent was filtered off and the final pH of the solution measured. The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was executed using a Jeol JSM-7000F Field Emission Scanning Electron

Microscope operated at an acceleration voltage of 15 kV. The samples were coated with a Pd-Pt layer sputtered with a Cressington 208HR high-resolution coater. Copper tape was used for samples preparations.

Solid-state ^1H MAS NMR spectra were collected at the magnetic field $B_0 = 14.1$ T (^1H Larmor frequency of 600.12 MHz) and MAS rate $\nu_r = 60.00$ kHz on a Bruker Avance-III spectrometer equipped with 1.3 mm MAS probehead. Acquisitions involved rotor-synchronized, double-adiabatic spin-echo sequence with 90° 1.25 μs excitation pulse followed by two 50.0 μs tanh/tan high-power adiabatic pulses (SHAPs) with 5 MHz frequency sweep.^{24,25} All pulses operated at the nutation frequency $\nu_{\text{nut}} = 200$ kHz. 128 signal transients with 5 s relaxation delay were accumulated for each spectrum. Shifts were referenced with respect to neat tetramethylsilane (TMS).

Batch adsorption of Co(II) ions. The adsorption behaviour of the sorbents materials was studied using the batch sorption technique. A stock solution of Co(II) was prepared by dissolving a known amount of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in deionized water. Different standards of concentration of metal ion solution were obtained by dilution of the stock solution with deionized water.

25 mL of Co(II) solution with known initial concentration were added to the sorbent (0.07 g for KL, LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂, 0.1 g for pure silica gel) and the suspension shaken in an Orbital Shaker-Incubator ES-20 from Grant-bio at 180 rpm to achieve equilibrium. The sorbent material was removed by filtration and the concentration of metal ions in the solutions determined spectrophotometrically using a Biochrom WPA S800+ Visible Spectrophotometer. The quantity of metal ions adsorbed on the sorbent surface was calculated from the difference between the initial concentration and the concentration in solution after adsorption at equilibrium. The adsorption capacity of the sorbent was calculated using the following equation:

$$q_{\text{eq}} = \frac{(c_0 - c_{\text{eq}}) \cdot V}{m_s} \quad (2)$$

where q_{eq} is the amount of Co(II) adsorbed per gram of sorbent ($\text{mg} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) at equilibrium, c_0 and c_{eq} are the initial and equilibrium Co(II) ion concentrations ($\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) in solution, V is the volume (L) of the initial metal ion solution and m_s is the weight of the sorbent (g). For determination of the pH effect on adsorption behavior of the sorbents, the pH of the initial metal ion solution was varied between 2 and 8 by adjusting the value by solution mixtures of 0.01 M HNO₃ and 0.01 M NH₄OH to dilute the stock solution to 50 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$. The suspensions were shaken for 3 h at room temperature (22 °C). Kinetic studies were carried out in neutral pH at room temperature for three different initial concentrations of Co(II) ion solution (20 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, 50 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, 100 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) with varying shaking times between 30 min and 24 h.

The pseudo-first, pseudo-second order and the Weber and Morris equations were applied to kinetics data of Co(II) ions adsorption on the synthesized sorbents. The pseudo-first-order equation:^{26,27}

$$\log(q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - \frac{kt}{2.303} \quad (3)$$

The pseudo-second-order equation:²⁸

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e} \quad (4)$$

where, q_e and q_t are the amounts of metal adsorbed ($\text{mg} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) at equilibrium time and at any instant of time t , K_1 ($\text{L} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) is the rate constant of the pseudo-first order adsorption and K_2 ($\text{g} \cdot \text{mg}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) is the pseudo-second order rate constant.

The Weber and Morris equation was used:²⁹

$$q_t = K_{\text{IPD}} t^{0.5} + C \quad (5)$$

where K_{IPD} is the intraparticle diffusion rate ($\text{mg} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{0.5}$) and C is a constant.

Adsorption isotherms were obtained by varying the initial Co(II) ion concentration between 2 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ and 160 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$. In order to determine the effect of temperature on the adsorption isotherms, three different temperatures (22 °C, 40 °C, 60 °C) at neutral pH (~7) and optimum pH (8) were used.

The sorption equilibrium data was applied to the Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin models. The linear form of the Langmuir model:³⁰

$$\frac{c_e}{q_e} = \frac{c_e}{q_0} + \frac{1}{K_L q_0} \quad (6)$$

where c_e is the equilibrium concentration of ions ($\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$), q_e is the amount of the adsorbed ions ($\text{mg} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$), and q_0 and K_L are adsorption capacity ($\text{mg} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) and the Langmuir isotherm constant ($\text{L} \cdot \text{mg}^{-1}$), respectively.

The Freundlich model:³¹

$$\log q_e = \log K_F + \frac{1}{n} \cdot \log c_e \quad (7)$$

where: K_F and n are the Freundlich constants related to the sorption capacity and sorption intensity, respectively.

The Temkin model of isotherm can be expressed as

$$c_s = \frac{RT}{b_T} \ln(K_T) + \frac{RT}{b_T} \ln c_{\text{eq}} \quad (8)$$

where c_s is the concentration of ions in the solid phase ($\text{mol} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$), b_T is the heat of adsorption ($\text{J} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$), K_T is the model constant ($\text{L} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$), R is the gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$), T represents the absolute temperature (°C), and c_{eq} denotes the equilibrium concentration of ions ($\text{mol} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) in the aqueous phase.³²

Desorption experiments. As desorbing agents three inorganic acids, 0.1 M HCl, 0.1 M H₂SO₄ and 0.1 M HNO₃, were used. For LS-SiO₂, 0.015 g of sorbent from the adsorption isotherm at 22 °C and neutral pH was given to 25 mL of desorbing agent. After the suspension was shaken for 2 h, the solid was filtered off and the amount of Co(II) ions in the filtrate was determined spectrophotometrically. The procedure was the same for KL-SiO₂, however, 0.02 g sorbent was used. The desorption percentage was calculated using equation (3).

$$D = \frac{m_{\text{des}}}{m_{\text{ads}}} \cdot 100 \% \quad (9)$$

where D is the desorption in percent, m_{des} the amount (mg) of Co(II) ions in the filtrate after desorption and m_{ads} the initial amount (mg) of Co(II) ions adsorbed on the sorbent.

UV/vis-spectroscopy. In order to determine the concentration of Co(II) ions in the filtrate after adsorption, 2 mL of fresh 4-(2'-Pyridylazo)resorcinol (PAR) solution (0.025 %, 0.25 $\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, 1.16 $\text{mol} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) were added to 3 mL of Na₂B₄O₇/NaOH-buffer (pH=9.8). The filtrate was added dropwise until an orange colouration was reached and diluted to the volume of 25 mL with de-ionized water. Before each measurement a calibration with solutions with known concentrations of metal ion was carried out. The wavelength was fixed at 500 nm (close to absorption maximum). Reproducibility of the measurements was determined in triplicate and the average values are reported.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis of the sorbent materials. Scheme 1 represents the crosslinking reaction of lignin with epichlorohydrin on the silica surface. Epoxidation of lignin in the presence of epichloro-

hydrin was studied and described in recent works.^{33–35} The reaction mechanism of epichlorohydrin with phenol, as a simplified structural model of lignin, has been previously studied.^{35–37} The crosslinking process of hydroxyl groups occurs through an opening of the epoxide ring by the phenoxy ion with further dehydrochlorination of chlorohydrinphenyl ether to phenylglycidyl ether. The consecutive reaction between the ether and the –OH groups of lignin results in formation of crosslinked lignin layer on the silica surface. Sodium carbonate acts as a catalyst for the reaction and neutralizes the side-products. For high reaction yield, the lignin initial solution should be saturated and the lignin:epichlorohydrin ratio should be rather low to prevent the production of epoxidized lignin instead of crosslinking of hydroxyl groups. Furthermore, higher epichlorohydrin concentrations could lead to epichlorohydrin oligomerization.³⁵

Influence of initial lignin solution concentration on the concentration of lignin in the composites. To understand the influence, lignosulfonate lignin with the initial concentration range from 1% to 10% was applied. Figure 1 presents % weight of immobilized LS in the final composites determined by TGA analysis in oxygen atmosphere. According to the collected data, an increased initial lignin concentration results in higher content of LS in final composites. The latter were synthesized with LS concentrations from 2 mg·g⁻¹ to 17 mg·g⁻¹.

Batch adsorption tests were carried out to investigate the influence of lignin concentration in LS-SiO₂ composites on the sorption efficiency for Co(II) ions. The adsorption capacity towards Co(II) ions increased with the amount of lignin in the LS-SiO₂; confirming that the functionality of lignin plays a decisive role in the adsorption processes (Figure 1). The highest initial concentration of lignin (10 %) was found to be the most appropriate for preparation of lignin-contained (LS or KL) composites for further investigations.

Characterization of the sorbent materials. TGA was applied for the determination of the lignin layer weight concentration in composite materials and to evaluate the thermal properties of the composites. TG-curves for composites as well as pure silica, KL, and LS are depicted in Figure 2.

All five TG-curves plotted show the minor weight loss of no more than 6% at temperatures up to 200 °C (Figure 2). This initial weight loss could be attributed to a gradual evaporation of moisture.³⁸ LS and KL start to decompose at higher temperatures. KL showed one gradual decomposition step starting at around 235 °C with a consecutive transition to a combustion step, which ended at around 510 °C with only 1.8 % of initial weight left. This residue was most likely due to impurities in the KL, which would only decompose at temperatures above 900 °C. In contrast, LS showed two more distinct decomposition steps starting at around 200 °C and 635 °C. Up to a temperature of 900 °C, LS only lost 53 % of its original weight which confirms the app. 47 % of ash content in used lignosulfonic acid (Figure 2a).

Neither of the two composites showed the second decomposition/combustion step found in the initial lignin derivatives. Likewise, the onset temperatures for the first decomposition step were shifted to slightly higher temperatures of 250 °C and 280 °C for LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂, respectively. This is most likely due to the high thermal stability of the silica. As shown on the Figure 2b, pure silica showed only gradual weight loss of 2.6 % because of the condensation of silica hydroxyl groups after the initial weight loss due to moisture.³⁸

Based on the 7.7 % overall weight loss for LS-SiO₂ and 10.2 % for KL-SiO₂, it can be concluded that both composites lost much less weight than the pure lignins, but slightly more than pure silica. As such, silica as basis material has greatly improved the thermal stability of the composite materials. From the difference in total weight loss between the composites and pure silica as well as the weight loss of the pure lignin compounds up to 900 °C, the amount of lignin in the composite sorbent materials, m_{lignin} , was calculated. For LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂, 17 and 37 mg lignin were immobilized per gram of sorbent, respectively. All major decomposition steps, their app. onset temperatures and the amount of lignin per gram of sorbent are summarized in Table 1.

Scheme 1. The scheme of lignosulfonate or kraft lignin crosslinking on the surface of silica gel.

Figure 1. Influence of LS concentration in LS-SiO₂ composite on adsorption efficiency towards Co(II) ions.

Figure 2. TGA curves of thermal decomposition in O₂ atmosphere for LS, KL, pure silica, LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂.

FTIR spectra were collected for pristine lignins and synthesized composites to confirm the immobilization and crosslinking of synthesized composites and pristine lignins (Figure 3). The FTIR spectra of all materials are characterized by broad bands at 3400 cm⁻¹ corresponding to -OH groups. The spectra of LS and KL lignins have some differences in the intensity of the characteristic bands due to the variations in lignin origin and content of functional groups. However, both spectra contain intense bands at 2920 cm⁻¹ and 2850 cm⁻¹ originating

from the presence of CH and methoxyl groups, respectively. Due to the hydrophilic nature of LS lignin, the characteristic band at 1370 cm⁻¹ related to the bending vibration of the phenolic hydroxyl groups is broader and of higher intensity. Similar curvature was observed for the bands at 1180, 1120 and 1050 cm⁻¹, corresponding to primary hydroxyl groups. According to previous studies, the characteristic peaks of the epoxy ring appeared distinctly at 1230-1280 cm⁻¹, 910 cm⁻¹, and 854 cm⁻¹.³³ The absence of those bands in the spectra of composites indicates a complete epichlorohydrin conversion during synthesis.

Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms and pore diameter distributions of the two synthesized composites LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂, as well as the silica precursor, were measured at -196 °C (Figure 4). In Figure 4a the nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms of pure silica and the two composites are plotted. Their pore-size distributions are depicted as pore volume plotted vs. pore diameter using the BJH method by the desorption branch (Figure 4b). All three nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms showed the typical shape of a type IV isotherm; as proposed by IUPAC.³⁹

This type describes a mesoporous material and is in line with the information of the silica beads manufacturer (pore size of 15 nm). This pore size is within the size range of mesopores given by IUPAC to be within the range of 2 and 50 nm.⁴⁰ The average pore diameter determined by BJH method, using the desorption branch for pure silica beads, was 11.3 nm and the pore size distribution for this material showed a distinct but rather broad peak at this pore diameter. The modification of the silica with LS and KL did not change the pore characteristics of the material significantly. For both composites, the average pore diameter augmented to 11.4 nm and 11.9 nm for KL-SiO₂ and LS-SiO₂, respectively. The overall shape and width of the pore size distribution was also maintained.

The BET surface area of pure silica was the highest with 275 m²·g⁻¹, while KL-SiO₂ had a slightly lower surface area of 266 m²·g⁻¹ and LS-SiO₂ had the lowest surface area of 240 m²·g⁻¹. In comparison, pristine KL had a surface area of 3.1 m²·g⁻¹,⁴¹ which is much less than the composite of KL and the silica gel. The similar trend as for the surface area could be observed for the total pore volume, which was 1 cm³·g⁻¹ for pure silica and 0.95 cm³·g⁻¹ for both composites. The lignin coating on the silica surface slightly lowered the pore volume of the composites in comparison to pure silica, however, this decrease was not significant. According to the results of the thermal analysis the amount of lignin per surface area for both new sorbents was calculated as 0.07 mg·m⁻² for LS-SiO₂ and 0.14 mg·m⁻² for KL-SiO₂.

Table 1. Characteristics of thermal decomposition in O₂ atmosphere of LS, KL, pure silica, LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂.

Material	T _{onset} , °C	Δm, %	Δm _{total} , %	Process	m _{lignin} , mg·g ⁻¹
LS	30	5.3	53	Evaporation of moisture ³⁸	
	200	30.2		First decomposition step of lignin	-
	635	17.5		Second decomposition step of lignin	
KL	30	5.5	98.2	Evaporation of moisture	
	235	31.7		Decomposition of lignin ³⁸	-
	435	61		Combustion of lignin ³⁸	
SiO ₂	30	3.9	6.5	Evaporation of moisture	
	300	2.6		Condensation of silica hydroxyl groups ³⁸	-
LS-SiO ₂	30	3.9	7.7	Evaporation of moisture	
	250	3.8		Condensation of silica hydroxyl groups and decomposition of lignin	17
KL-SiO ₂	30	5.5	10.2	Evaporation of moisture	
	280	4.7		Condensation of silica hydroxyl groups and decomposition of lignin	37

Figure 3. FTIR spectra of initial lignins and synthesized lignin-contained composites.

The obtained data suggest that the lignin coating simulates the textural features of initial silica without blocking of pristine pores. Such surface tailoring induces additional functionality to the surface due to the phenolic, carboxylic, sulphuric or thiol groups of the macromolecules. Functionality and textural features are the crucial parameters for sorbent materials and affect its sorption efficiency. Thus, the proposed synthetic pathway yields materials that maintain the similar textural and thermal characteristics of initial silica, but exhibit higher functionality due to the lignin overlayer. This renders the composites as prospective sorbents for metal ion adsorption, such as Co(II) ions.⁴¹

Figure 4. N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms and pore diameter distributions for pure silica, LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂.

The SEM micrographs in Figure 5 shows that the lignin-contained composites have a heterogeneous surface structure with several irregularities. Especially KL-SiO₂ shows a rough structure with some porosity. This morphology can be seen to a lesser extent for LS-SiO₂. Since the results of TGA measured previously showed that there is a lower amount of lignin in this composite in comparison to KL-SiO₂, these surface textures most likely stem from the lignin. The rough surface

texture and the fact that the lignin with its functional groups is present on the sorbent's surface should be beneficial for the adsorption of Co(II) ions. The results of EDS analysis (Figure 6) from the surface region of lignin-containing composites showed uniform carbon distribution. This indicates a uniform coating of lignin on the surface of silica.

Figure 5. SEM images of (a) LS-SiO₂ and (b) KL-SiO₂.

Figure 6. SEM EDS images of (a) LS-SiO₂ and (b) KL-SiO₂.

Investigation of efficiency as sorbents for Co(II) recycling:

Effect of pH on the adsorption behavior. The determination of pH_{pzc} provides information on the surface charge of the material (Figure 7). The pH_{pzc} for KL-SiO₂ and LS-SiO₂ was found to be almost identical with 8.45 and 8.50, respectively. At the pH_{pzc} , the charge of the positive and negative surface groups is equal, giving a neutral surface charge in total. When the pH is below pH_{pzc} , the total surface charge of the solids is positive.⁴² In light of the competition between protons and the positively charged metal ions for the active sites on the sorbent surface, this surface charge is not favourable.⁹ However, Co(II) ions are known to precipitate as insoluble Co(OH)₂ in basic media, which makes it difficult to operate at pH 9 or above.

The effect of pH on the adsorption behaviour of both synthesized sorbents, LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂, was studied. The pH was adjusted between 2 and 8 by mixtures of 0.01 M HNO₃ and 0.01 M NH₄OH. The effect of higher pH was not studied to prevent errors in measurement due to the formation of solid

Co(OH)₂ in strongly basic medium and composites degradation as a result of silica decomposition. Aqueous ammonia solution has been chosen over sodium hydroxide in order to prevent precipitation of cobalt(II) as Co(OH)₂. In presence of chosen buffer solution cobalt(II) ions form positively charged aminocomplexes, which could interact with negatively charged surface of lignin-silica materials similar to the metal water complexes found in neutral to slightly acidic medium.⁴³

Figure 7. Determination of pH_{pzc} for KL-SiO₂ and LS-SiO₂.

Figure 8. Effect of pH on the adsorption of Co(II) by (a) LS-SiO₂ and (b) KL-SiO₂.

In Figure 8 the adsorption capacity of Co(II) per gram sorbent is plotted vs the initial pH of metal ion solution. The amount of adsorbed Co(II) ions per gram of LS-SiO₂ increased

slightly with the pH value from $8.2 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ to $8.8 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ at pH 7. At pH 8, a jump in adsorption capacity to $11.2 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ was clearly visible. For KL-SiO₂, the adsorption capacity decreased linearly from pH 8 to 4. At pH 2, however, the capacity was much lower than expected for a linear decline. After adsorption the sorbent was much brighter in colour at pH 2 than at higher pH-values, where the sorbent showed the same dark brown colour as the pure sorbent before adsorption. Consequently, it could be suspected that the sorbent is not stable in strongly acidic media, leading inevitably to lower sorption capacity. The low stability of the sorbent could be caused by lignin leaching from the surface due to the destruction of epoxide linkages. Overall, the adsorption capacity of KL-SiO₂ was highest at pH 8 with a value of $15.4 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ (86.9 %), whereas for LS-SiO₂ is able to adsorb $11.2 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ (63.1 %) of Co(II) ions at the same conditions (Figure 8).

Both sorbents showed an increase in adsorption capacity with rising pH, and the optimum pH value was found to be 8. This originates from the competition between the metal ions and protons for the phenolic, carboxylic and sulfuric functional groups on the lignin surface.⁹ Since for LS-SiO₂ the pH_{pzc} was 8.50 and for KL-SiO₂ it was 8.45 (*vide supra*), the total surface charge of the composites was positive at pH 8. However, when the pH approaches closer to the pH_{pzc} , the overall charge gets lower, either due to the formation of negatively charged surface groups or the deprotonation of positively charged surface groups. This enables a greater uptake of Co(II) ions at higher pH.

Effect of shaking time. In order to determine the optimum adsorption time for the two sorbents, the shaking time was varied for three different initial concentrations of Co(II) ions in solution at neutral pH. Eight different time intervals between 15 min and 24 h were chosen. The adsorption capacities of LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂ in $\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ were plotted as a function of shaking time (Figure 9).

The adsorption capacity increased rapidly for shaking times up to 1.5 h for LS-SiO₂. After 15 min of shaking with an initial metal ion concentration of $100 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, LS-SiO₂ had an adsorption capacity of $31.5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ which increased to $34.3 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ after 1.5 h. This effect was more pronounced for higher initial concentration of Co(II) ions in solution. The difference between the adsorption capacities after 15 min and 1.5 h was $0.3 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for an initial Co(II) ion concentration of $20 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, while at $50 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ the difference amounted to $1.5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ and for $100 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ it was $2.8 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. This rapid adsorption of metal ions onto the sorbent can be attributed to the high number of coordination sites available on the high surface area of the composite. Since the coordination sites were vacant in the beginning, a large amount of Co(II) could be adsorbed in a matter of minutes. At low concentrations of Co(II) ions in solution, this amounted to almost all of the ions and the difference in adsorption capacity between shorter and longer shaking times was thus very low. The adsorption equilibrium was reached after only one hour of shaking time. When the metal ion concentration in solution increased, it also took longer to adsorb these ions due to their higher quantity. Furthermore, the Co(II) ions already adsorbed on the surface slowed the adsorption of additional ions from the solution due to repulsive interactions.⁴⁴ Consequently, it took a longer time to reach equilibrium and a stronger increase in adsorption capacity could be observed.

Figure 9. Effect of shaking time on the adsorption of Co(II) by (a) LS-SiO₂ and (b) KL-SiO₂.

At shaking times higher than 1.5 h the adsorbed amount of Co(II) ions on LS-SiO₂ was almost constant with only minor fluctuations attributed to inaccuracy of the UV/Vis-analysis. Since even higher initial concentrations of Co(II) ions are to be used to determine the effect of initial concentration, a shaking time of 6 h was used in all subsequent experiments with this sorbent to ensure that adsorption equilibrium was definitely achieved.

For KL-SiO₂, the differences in adsorption capacity between shorter and longer shaking times were even lower than for LS-SiO₂. For an initial Co(II) ion concentration of $100 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ the difference in adsorption capacity after 15 min and 1 h was $0.17 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, while for initial Co(II)-concentrations of 50 and $20 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ the difference amounted to only $0.1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. Due to an even higher surface area in comparison to LS-SiO₂, more coordination sites are exposed on the surface of this sorbent. More metal ions could be adsorbed initially and thus the difference in adsorption capacities for KL-SiO₂ at short shaking times was lower than for LS-SiO₂. At longer shaking times, the adsorption capacities for both sorbents were very similar. The adsorption capacity was almost constant at shaking times higher than 1 h. In order to be able to compare the results of later experiments of the two sorbents, a shaking time of 6 h as determined for LS-SiO₂ was employed in all further experiments with this sorbent.

The adsorption rate is the critical parameter in order to predict the efficiency of adsorption with the influence of time. It provides valuable data of the efficiency of adsorbent and provides information regarding the efficiency at larger scale. The

adsorption kinetics of Co(II) ions on the silica coated by lignin was studied by application of pseudo-first, pseudo-second-order equations and intraparticle diffusion model to understand the mechanisms of adsorption and rate-controlling step of the process (Figure 10). The parameters were calculated from the fitting experimental data with applied kinetic models (Table 2). The high values of correlation coefficients from lineal fitting (R^2 higher than 0.99) confirm that the pseudo-second equation kinetic model fits very well the kinetics data and could be applied for the description of the adsorption kinetics of Co(II) ions on silica coated by LS or KL lignin.

It could be seen from the plots for the intraparticle diffusion model that it is nonlinear, which confirms that both strong interactions and the boundary layer diffusion could determine the rate of adsorption. Correlation coefficient (R^2) were found to be lower than 0.43 for all studied systems.

Adsorption equilibrium study: effect of initial Co(II) ion concentration. The effect of initial concentration of Co(II) ions on the adsorption behavior of LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂ as well as pure KL and silica was studied at room temperature and in neutral pH. The initial concentrations used ranged between 2 mg·L⁻¹ and 160 mg·L⁻¹. Since Co(II) was adsorbed from aqueous medium, LS could not be used as a sorbent material as it is soluble in water. Figure 11 shows the average equilibrium adsorption capacity plotted vs. the equilibrium concentration of Co(II) remaining in the solution after adsorption had taken place. These adsorption isotherms of the synthesized lignin-silica composites as well as pure silica and KL are shown, too. At low initial concentrations, the increase in adsorption capacity for the composites was very steep, confirming the high affinity of the composite surface to the Co(II) ions. With rising initial metal ion concentration, the uptake of Co(II) slowed down, indicating that a smaller amount of adsorption sites was available than at the beginning.

The adsorption capacities at high initial concentrations were also much closer to each other, implying that the absolute maximum in adsorption capacity was almost achieved. To a lesser extent this development could also be observed for KL and pure silica. For low initial concentrations, the increase of the adsorption capacity was not as steep and the difference towards the behavior at high initial concentrations was not as pronounced as for the composites. It could be seen from the isotherms presented in Figure 11 that the affinity of Co(II) ions is much higher for composites in comparison to un-modified silica or kraft lignin. The similarities in isotherms shape for both composites could be associated with the active adsorption sites for both composites are carboxyl and hydroxyl (–COOH and –OH) groups, as well as sulphonic (–SO₃⁻) groups in liginosulfonate and thiol (–SH) groups in kraft lignin.

Effect of temperature. Taking into account that higher temperature is common for industrial wastewaters, an influence of increased temperature to adsorption was studied. The isotherms, which were measured at 22 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C in neutral pH and at pH 8, are presented in Figure 12. The adsorption isotherms of the sorbents towards Co(II) showed different shapes and trends depending on both temperature and pH. In neutral pH for both sorbents the adsorption capacity was highest at 60 °C. The highest experimental adsorption capacity was found to be 53.9 mg·g⁻¹ (94.5%) for LS-SiO₂ and 52.6 mg·g⁻¹ (92.8%) for KL-SiO₂. These values are much higher than the adsorption capacities for pure biosorbents (22 mg·g⁻¹, lemon peel)⁴⁵ and lignin modified by alkali glycerol delignification (7.7 mg·g⁻¹)¹⁸. Therefore, the combination of silica and lignin

in the new sorbent materials presented in this work shows high potential for the adsorption of Co(II) ions from aqueous solution.

For LS-SiO₂ the lowest adsorption capacities could be found for 22 °C, indicating thus an endothermic process. This behavior has also been reported in previous studies of the temperature effect on the adsorption of Co(II).^{3,46} However, this difference in adsorption capacities for the different temperatures could only be observed at high initial concentrations of Co(II) ions in solution. At lower initial Co(II) ion concentration, the adsorption capacities at different temperatures did not show significant differences. This is a known phenomenon for sorbent materials during the adsorption process.^{3,46}

Table 2. Kinetic parameters for the adsorption of Co(II) ions on the LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂ composite (initial concentration of cobalt: 10 – 50 mg·L⁻¹).

Kinetics model	Parameter symbol, unit	Initial Co(II) conc., mg·L ⁻¹		
		20	50	100
LS-SiO₂				
Pseudo-first order	$q_{es, cal}, mg \cdot g^{-1}$	12.49	2.63	1.36
	$K_1, l \cdot min^{-1}$	0.024	0.023	0.169
	R^2	0.007	0.028	0.491
Pseudo-second order	$q_{es, cal}, mg \cdot g^{-1}$	6.84	17.48	34.97
	$K_2, g \cdot mg^{-1} \cdot min^{-1}$	4.18	2.72	0.62
	R^2	0.999	0.999	1.000
Intraparticle diffusion model	$K_{IPD}, mg \cdot g^{-1} \cdot min^{-0.5}$	0.05	0.15	0.47
	C	6.74	16.92	33.08
	R^2	0.239	0.177	0.426
CFBL-SiO₂				
Pseudo-first order	$q_{es, cal}, mg \cdot g^{-1}$	6.82	2.27	2.75
	$K_1, l \cdot min^{-1}$	0.005	0.002	0.058
	R^2	0.001	0.001	0.355
Pseudo-second order	$q_{es, cal}, mg \cdot g^{-1}$	6.88	17.45	34.48
	$K_2, g \cdot mg^{-1} \cdot min^{-1}$	4.69	3.28	0.76
	R^2	1.000	0.999	0.999
Intraparticle diffusion model	$K_{IPD}, mg \cdot g^{-1} \cdot min^{-0.5}$	0.05	0.15	0.47
	C	6.74	16.92	33.08
	R^2	0.239	0.177	0.426

Figure 10. (a,b) Pseudo-first order plots, (c,d) pseudo-second order plots and (e,f) intraparticle diffusion plots for Co(II) ions adsorption kinetics by LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂.

Figure 11. Adsorption isotherms of Co(II) on LS-SiO₂, KL-SiO₂, KL and pure silica at room temperature.

Contrariwise, the isotherm at 22 °C in neutral pH for KL-SiO₂ showed slightly higher adsorption capacities than the isotherm at 40 °C over the whole range. The difference was rather small with a maximum gap of 0.6 mg·g⁻¹. The adsorption capacities at the two lower temperatures can be seen as very similar to each other in contrast to the much higher adsorption capacities found at 22 °C. This hints again towards an endothermic process where temperatures above 40 °C are required. At pH 8, the shape of isotherms of adsorption was changed from L-type to S-type, which confirms that more complex character of the mechanism. Although the adsorption capacities were higher at 22 °C than at 40 °C for both LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂, the irregularity found for the isotherms at 60 °C makes it difficult to determine the overall effect of temperature on the adsorption behavior at pH 8.

The estimation of adsorption parameters and quantitative comparison of adsorbent performance for different systems can be elucidated by application of variable models for adsorption isotherms. This allows to establish the most appropriate adsorption equilibrium correlation to describe the interaction of ions with the surface of materials. Calculated parameters are important for optimization of the adsorption mechanism pathways, expression of the surface properties and capacities of adsorbents, and design of the adsorption systems.³²

The three common isotherm models of Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin were applied to the present systems. The characteristic parameters were calculated for each isotherm model and summarized in Table 3. All systems where Co(II) ions are present in form of aqua complexes (de-ionized water) were fitted well to the Langmuir isotherm model. The fitting was confirmed by the high values of correlation coefficients (0.96-0.99). The systems where Co(II) ions were adsorbed by in presence of ammonia buffer, i.e. pH 8.0 and in form of ammonia complexes, could be described well by the Freundlich isotherm model (R^2 from 0.948–0.985 for 22–40 °C and 0.721–0.878 for 60 °C). Additionally, it was found that the correlation coefficients are decreasing with the increasing of temperature for the systems with and without the addition of ammonia ions. Those observations let to conclude that in natural media (in de-ionized water), the monolayer adsorption on a homogeneous surface is taking place if no interactions between the adsorbed ions are presented. With the addition of ammonia buffer, more groups are responsible for adsorption and the surface becomes more heterogeneous. This results eventually in multilayer adsorption with non-uniform distribution of adsorption heat.

Figure 12. Adsorption isotherms of Co(II) on LS-SiO₂ in (a) neutral pH and (b) pH 8 and on KL-SiO₂ in (c) neutral pH and (d) pH 8 for three different temperatures (22 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C).

Based on the applied Langmuir isotherm model, the capacity of the monolayer (q_m) was found to be 52.63 mg·g⁻¹ at 22 °C, 58.14 mg·g⁻¹ at 40 °C and 75.19 mg·g⁻¹ at 60 °C for LS-SiO₂ composite and slightly lower for KL-SiO₂ composite: 50.76 mg·g⁻¹ at 22 °C, 56.18 mg·g⁻¹ at 40 °C and 59.52 mg·g⁻¹ at 60 °C. The adsorption of Co(II) onto the surface of bio-inorganic composites was favorable according to the values of R_L : $0 \leq R_L \leq 1$.

The heat of adsorption of cobalt(II) ions on the composites was decreased from 330 to 241 J·mol⁻¹ and from 335 to 189 J·mol⁻¹ with increasing temperature for KL-SiO₂ in de-ionized water or at pH 8.0, respectively. For the LS-SiO₂ sample, the tendency was found the same but the values of the heat of adsorption were slightly lower: from 239 to 141 J·mol⁻¹ (in de-ionized water) and from 247 to 93.8 J·mol⁻¹ (pH 8.0) for the

temperature range from 22 to 60 °C. The maximum binding energy for interactions between the lignin-coated silica surface and cobalt ions (K_T) was observed at the lowest applied temperature 22 °C for all systems.

Taking into account the low concentrations of immobilized lignin, i.e. 22.9 mg of liginosulfonate and 37.6 mg of kraft lignin per gram of silica, and assuming that the functional groups of lignin are acting as adsorption sites for the cobalt(II) ions, the maximum loading of the macromolecule was calculated. Accordingly, 3.3 mg and 1.6 mg of cobalt per one mg of the LS and KL monolayer on the solid surface could be recovered, respectively. Such high values of capacity of the immobilized lignin could be explained by accessibility augmentation of functional groups for the stretched macromolecule on the solid surface. The same effect was found in our previous studies regarding immobilized lignin and chitosan on silica surfaces for adsorption of organic and inorganic pollutants.^{23,47,48}

Table 3. The isotherm models parameters obtained for Co(II) ions adsorption onto LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂ sorbent

Isotherm model/ unit	Co(II), de-ionized water			Co(II), ammonia buffer, pH 8.0		
	22 °C	40 °C	60 °C	22 °C	40 °C	60 °C
LS-SiO₂						
Langmuir						
q_m , mg·g ⁻¹	52.63	58.14	75.19	–	–	–
K_L , L·mg ⁻¹	0.499	0.494	0.308	–	–	–
R_L , L·mg ⁻¹	0.039	0.039	0.061	–	–	–
R ²	0.994	0.985	0.968	0.055	0.003	0.029
Freundlich						
K_F , mg·g ⁻¹	7.78	8.12	7.49	1.75	1.71	1.53
1/n	0.766	0.835	1.183	1.103	1.035	2.128
R ²	0.731	0.670	0.640	0.985	0.961	0.721
Temkin						
b_T , J·mol ⁻¹	239.4	210.4	141.7	247.9	233.7	93.8
K_T , L·g ⁻¹	3.903	3.532	2.285	1.536	1.138	1.119
R ²	0.816	0.777	0.809	0.824	0.881	0.850
KL- SiO₂						
Langmuir						
q_m , mg·g ⁻¹	50.76	56.18	59.52	55.87	53.76	–
K_L , L·mg ⁻¹	0.495	0.195	0.715	0.062	0.050	–
R_L , L·mg ⁻¹	0.039	0.093	0.027	0.243	0.286	–
R ²	0.980	0.972	0.967	0.890	0.909	0.013
Freundlich						
K_F , mg·g ⁻¹	10.26	5.03	14.27	3.19	2.35	3.10
1/n	0.555	0.880	0.805	0.744	0.782	1.286
R ²	0.560	0.785	0.616	0.948	0.964	0.878
Temkin						
b_T , J·mol ⁻¹	330.55	215.87	241.22	335.26	339.12	189.91
K_T , L·g ⁻¹	9.527	2.296	7.534	2.697	1.871	1.891
R ²	0.651	0.901	0.575	0.898	0.882	0.670

Complementary analysis of the adsorption process was investigated by means of solid-state ^1H MAS NMR (Figure 13). The spectra for the bio-inorganic composites before Co(II) adsorption reveal a narrow signal around 1 ppm corresponding to $-\text{OH}$ groups terminating silica surface. Resonances in the range of 2–6 ppm originate from different conformations of H_2O molecules present at the surface and organic surface-modifier moieties. The spectra after Co(II) adsorption exhibit dramatically reduced resolution and sensitivity as a consequence of interactions with unpaired electrons of Co(II) ions. As such, the solid-state ^1H MAS NMR spectra clearly prove the presence of adsorbed cobalt species at the adsorbents surface.

Figure 13. Solid-state ^1H MAS NMR spectra of KL-SiO₂ and LS-SiO₂ adsorbent materials before (black traces) and after cobalt(II) ions adsorption process (red traces).

Desorption Experiments. The desorption study was conducted in order to understand the ability of sorbent to be applied multiple times. In this study, only the possibility of desorption was

CONCLUSION

We have demonstrated a rapid synthetic strategy for fabrication of lignin coatings on silica. The process of lignin deposition was optimized for hydrophobic (kraft lignin – KL) and hydrophilic (lignosulfonate – LS) lignins. The proposed one-step procedure was found to be an easy and effective method for thin lignin layer immobilization on solid surfaces. It was found that even a low concentration of lignin (17 mg of LS or 37 mg of KL per one g of SiO₂) on the silica surface is sufficient for effective cobalt(II) removal. The adsorption behavior of silica coated by two types of lignin towards Co(II) ions in aqueous solution was studied. The results showed that combination of lignosulfonate or kraft lignin with silica gel results in strong synergistic effects toward cobalt(II) removal. The time for reaching of equilibrium was found to be 1.5 h for LS-SiO₂ and 1 h for KL-SiO₂, which is close to the characteristics of inorganic sorbents. The studied adsorption of cobalt(II) ions at neutral medium was found to be an endothermic process and the maximum adsorption capacity was found to be 75 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$

tested without optimizing the experimental conditions. To this end, samples of both composites materials with known amounts of Co(II) ions adsorbed on their surfaces were exposed to three different desorbing agents for 2 h at room temperature (Figure 14). The desorbing agents used were 0.1 M HCl, 0.1 M H₂SO₄, and 0.1 M HNO₃.

Figure 14. Desorption of Co(II) from LS-SiO₂ and KL-SiO₂ by 0.1 M HCl, 0.1 M H₂SO₄, and 0.1 M HNO₃. The amount of Co(II) desorbed from the sorbents by the different acids is given in percentage of the initial amount of adsorbed Co(II) .

While the desorption was possible for all combinations of acids and sorbents, all desorption percentages were below 40%. The highest desorption was observed when KL-SiO₂ was exposed to 0.1 M HNO₃ (38.9%). This sorbent showed discoloration after exposure to all three acids used, which has already been observed when testing the adsorption behavior at pH 2 and is most likely due to the sorbent material being unstable in strongly acidic media. For LS-SiO₂ the best desorbing agent was HCl, with a percentage of 37.5%, followed closely by H₂SO₄ with 36.8%. Desorbing cobalt from the sorbents is possible, even though KL-SiO₂ shows degeneration. Although the desorption percentages are too low for commercial use, this instability generally known for inorganic and polymeric sorbents. The low efficiency in desorbing Co(II) ions probably stems from the short exposure time of only 2 h.

and 59 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for the LS- or KL-coated silica at 60 °C, respectively. Our results show that the adsorption capacity of composites is higher than the capacity of initial silica (20 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) and kraft lignin (27 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$). Despite of two times lower concentration of LS coating on silica surface, the calculated adsorption capacity of immobilized LS was much higher (4.4 $\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) than for KL (1.6 $\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), which could be explained by presence of sulphonic groups in lignosulfonate lignin. The high adsorption capacity is promising when comparing to the adsorption capacities of other sorbents; as well as inorganics and ion-exchangers towards Co(II) reported in the literature. The desorption study proved that cobalt(II) could be successfully recovered after sorbents application. The critical advancement of this work is the demonstration of synthesis and physical characterization of lignin-based coatings, which could find an application beyond the scope of cobalt ion removal.⁴⁹

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